

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES OF BUILDING CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY AND ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN THIS AREA

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ANNOTATION Studies in developing countries show that 30-40% of natural resources are utilized in the construction industry and 50% of energy is used for heating and cooling buildings. If energy demand can be reduced or industry can be slowed down, energy consumption will be reduced. Therefore, you need to set this energy consumption policy to control energy consumption. The purpose of this study is to measure energy consumption and intensity in the construction industry.

Key words: building construction, urbanization, energy consumption, stringency, extreme temperatures, Zero-carbon-ready, energy efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

The operations of buildings account for 30% of global final energy consumption and 26% of global energy-related emissions (8% being direct emissions in buildings and 18% indirect emissions from the production of electricity and heat used in buildings). Direct emissions from the buildings sector decreased in 2022 compared to the year before, despite extreme temperatures driving up heating-related emissions in certain regions [1]. In 2022, buildings sector energy use increased by around 1%. Minimum performance standards and building energy codes are increasing in scope and stringency across countries, and the use of efficient and renewable buildings technologies is accelerating. Yet the sector needs more rapid changes to get on track with the Net Zero Emissions by 2050 (NZE) Scenario. This decade is crucial for implementing the measures required to achieve the targets of all new buildings and 20% of the existing building stock being zero-carbon-ready by 2030 [2].

Building construction is one of the most dynamic economic sectors, generating wealth and income and contributing highly to the global development. Financial and commercial activities related to construction, renovation and management of buildings, development of infrastructure and of urban projects, and extension of assets currently represent a budget close to 9 trillion US dollars (HIS, 2013), which is expected to increase up to 11 trillion US Dollars by 2023 [2] and up to 15 trillion US Dollars by 2025 [3]. Most of the investments are directed to the residential sector, with 70% of the total budget spent by the public sector, 26% are private investments and the rest is covered by official development assistance sources [4].

- Energy sector CO₂ emissions include emissions from energy combustion and industrial processes.
- Zero-carbon-ready buildings are highly energy-efficient and resilient buildings that either use renewable energy directly, or rely on a source of energy supply that can be fully decarbonised, such as electricity or district energy. The zero-carbon-ready concept include both operational and embodied emissions.

The buildings and construction sector accounts for about 36% of the global energy consumption. Accounting the energy spent for construction and demolition, the energy share is increasing up to 50% of the total energy consumption [15]. Despite the significant energy conservation measures undertaken by the developed countries, the energy demand of buildings increased more than 20% between 2000 and 2017, as a result of the rapidly growing floor area of dwellings, the relatively small reduction of the energy intensity and the rising energy requirements of the energy services [16]. Future scenarios on the energy consumption of buildings propose pathways to minimize the energy consumption of the sector by 2050 or later, through intensive use of clean electricity and improved energy efficiency measures in buildings. However, such an objective requires adoption of intensive

green policies and a considerable increase of investments. No clear engagements or even promises towards the adoption of such policies are undertaken and there is a real risk that the energy consumption and the production of greenhouse gases of the building sector will continue to increase.

The construction growth rate during 2019 and 2020 was 2.6% instead of the predicted 3.2%, a slowdown associated with the COVID19 pandemic and the decrease of the related construction activities in North America, Europe and China [5]. Buildings and construction accounts for about 13% of the world gross domestic product (GDP) and it is expected to rise up to 15% in the near future [3,5].

METHOD

About half of the construction output is generated by developing countries and emerging economies facing a significant population increase, urbanization and rising living standards, like India, China and Brazil [6].

1-figure. Energy consumption in buildings by fuel in the Net Zero Scenario, 2010-2030

Advances in energy efficiency are key to boosting progress in decoupling energy consumption from floor area growth [7-8].

The building sector is facing serious economic, environmental, technical, and social challenges caused mainly by the unprecedented global and regional climate change, overpopulation, intensive urbanization, excessive use of resources and social inequalities. The potential responses to these challenges and the policies to follow will shape the present and future quality of life of several billion people and will define to a great extent the future socioeconomic pathways and the magnitude of the global growth. We consider that the major challenges and potential future opportunities in the built environment are the ones described in the following paragraphs.

2-Figure. Global floor area and buildings energy intensity in the Net Zero Scenario, 2010-2030

Although there is a vast political agreement that future energy scenarios should mainly focus on environmental sustainability issues and promote decarbonization objectives, national policies and priorities around the world differ considerably. Issues related to short or long-term national interests outweigh the global sustainability objectives. Issues related to security and affordability of the future energy supply aiming to feed a fast economic development, lack of

resources to implement clean energy generation plants and finance the energy rehabilitation of the building sector, fears about the future cost of the clean energy supply and of the related innovative energy systems, concerns about the future technological dependence from the advanced energy actors, etc., are amongst the arguments used to deviate from the normative decarbonization approaches.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Very few countries have developed and implement a long vision of decarbonization policies supported by measures aiming to alter and boost the local infrastructure and technological know-how. As a result, since 2017, about two-thirds of the world's countries have not set up mandatory building energy regulations and certification schemes, and only 73 countries have introduced mandatory energy legislation [16]. Lack of appropriate legislative measures delays the market adaptation to the new technologies and adds more stock of high energy buildings. As reported by IEA [16], the number of new, high-efficiency buildings being constructed needs to increase more than 25-fold by 2030, with deep energy renovation of existing stock also needing to more than double in the coming decade.

By 2030, global floor area is expected to increase by around 15%, equivalent to the entire built floor area of North America today. Around 80% of this floor area growth is expected to be in emerging market and developing economies [9].

3-figure. . Modelled global residential energy demand for heating and for air conditioning in a reference scenario [10].

At the same time, to get on track with the NZE Scenario, the energy intensity of the buildings sector needs to decline nearly five times more quickly over the next decade than it has in the past decade. This means the energy consumed per square metre in 2030 must be around 35% less than in 2022 [11-12].

CONCLUSION

The construction sector improves people's social lives, while creating jobs, protecting welfare and health, and making an important contribution to global economic development. Human activities in the built environment consume energy and other material resources, generate pollution and waste, and impact global and local environmental quality. Human social dynamics reflect the realities of the construction sector and determine its challenges, opportunities and overall operating balance. Societal developments related to population growth, global and regional overheating and climate change, poverty and economic vulnerability, social exclusion and associated migration flows require organized and efficient responses.

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